

RHOTRIX EIGEN VALUES AND EIGEN VECTORS

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Abstract:

This paper presents a new technique for solving Eigen values and Eigen vectors by the concept of rhotrix. Use of rhotrices in the above mentioned problems reduces the computational cost and time complexity to a greater extent by solving two such problems simultaneously.

1. Introduction:

Mathematical arrays that are in some way between two-dimensional vectors and 2x2 dimensional matrices were suggested by Atanassov and Shannon [1]. As an extension to this idea, Ajibade [2] introduced an array system that lies between 2x2 dimensional matrices and 3x3 dimensional matrices called 'Rhotrix'[3,4]. A rhotrix as given in [1] is of the form

$$R = \left\langle \begin{matrix} a \\ b & h(R) & d \\ e \end{matrix} \right\rangle$$

where a,b,d,e,h(R) are all real numbers and h (R) is called the heart of a rhotrix R. The rhotrix R given above is called the base rhotrix. It was also mentioned in [2] that a rhotrix can be extended to n-dimension. The n-dimensional rhotrix is denoted by $R_n = \langle a_{ij}, c_{lk} \rangle$ where, a_{ij} and c_{lk} represent the elements and $|R_n| = \frac{n^2+1}{2}$ ($i, j=1,2,3,\dots,t$ and $(l, k=1,2,3,\dots t-1)$. The value of t is given as $t=(n+1)/2$. An alternative to the multiplication proposed by Sani [4] followed by its generalization in [5]. The method of converting rhotrix to coupled matrix was suggested by Sani [6]. His idea was found useful to solve systems of $t \times t$ and $(t-1) \times (t-1)$ matrix problems simultaneously, $n \in 2z^++1$ and $t = \frac{n^2+1}{2}$. The inverse of rhotrix is given in [2] by Ajibade as, if for any two rhotrices P and Q, we have $P \circ Q = I$, then Q is the inverse of P.

That is, $Q = P^{-1} = \frac{-1}{(h(P))^2} \left\langle \begin{matrix} a \\ b & -h(P) & d \\ e \end{matrix} \right\rangle$

And the inverse of rhotrix is given in [4] by Sani as, if $R_3 = \left\langle \begin{matrix} a \\ b & h(R) & d \\ e \end{matrix} \right\rangle$ then

$$R_3^{-1} = \left\langle \begin{matrix} \frac{e}{ae-bd} \\ \frac{b}{bd-ae} & \frac{1}{h(R)} & \frac{d}{bd-ae} \\ \frac{a}{ae-bd} \end{matrix} \right\rangle$$

Hence R_3 and P_3 are similar

2. Rhotrix Eigen Values and Eigen Vector:

In this Sani.B gave a generalization of the row column multiplication method for n-dimensional rhotrices was presented as an extension of earlier work on row-column multiplication for base level rhotrices of dimension three. The idea was used to introduce the eigenvector , eigenvalue problem in rhotrices.

Definition:

The main rhotrix column vector is represented as $\langle x^{nj} \rangle$ and the main row vectors represented as $\langle x^{in} \rangle$ where $i, j = 1,2,\dots,t$ with $t = (n+1)/2$. Similarly the other columns and which are not the main are defined as follows $\langle x^{n-1,k} \rangle$ and $\langle x^{1,n-1} \rangle$ respectively where $k, l = 1,2,\dots,t-1$.

Theorem:

Let λ be an eigenvalue of a rhotrix R_n with the corresponding eigenvector $\langle x^{nj} \rangle$ then if k is a positive integer, λ^k is an eigenvalue of the rhotrix R_n^k with the corresponding eigenvector $\langle x^{nj} \rangle$

Proof:

$$\begin{aligned} R_n^k \langle x^{nj} \rangle &= R_n^{k-1} R_n \langle x^{nj} \rangle \\ &= R_n^{k-1} \lambda \langle x^{nj} \rangle \\ &= R_n^{k-2} R_n \lambda \langle x^{nj} \rangle \\ &= R_n^{k-1} \lambda^2 \langle x^{nj} \rangle \\ &\vdots \\ &= R_n \lambda^{k-1} \langle x^{nj} \rangle \\ &= \lambda^{k-1} R_n \langle x^{nj} \rangle \\ R_n^k \langle x^{nj} \rangle &= \lambda^k \langle x^{nj} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Therefore is an eigenvalue of the rhotix R_n^k with the corresponding eigenvector $\langle x^{nj} \rangle$

Theorem:

For any given matrix $A = \begin{bmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ g & h & i \end{bmatrix}_{3 \times 3}$ if

λ_1, λ_2 and λ_3 are the Eigen value of A, then

$$\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3$$

$$\lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2 \lambda_3 + \lambda_3 \lambda_1 = \lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2 \lambda_3 + \lambda_3 \lambda_1$$

$$\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 = \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 - \{ bdi + afh - (bfg + dhc) \}$$

where $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ are Eigen value of its corresponding rhotrix

Proof:

Characteristic equation of A is $|A - \lambda I| = 0$

$$\Rightarrow \begin{vmatrix} a - \lambda & b & c \\ d & e - \lambda & f \\ g & h & i - \lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow (a-\lambda)[(e-\lambda)(i-\lambda)-hf]-b[di-d\lambda-gf]+c[dh-ge+g\lambda] = 0$$

Simplifying this we get

$$\lambda^3 - (a+e+i)\lambda^2 + (ai+ei-gc-hf+ae-bd)\lambda - (aei-ahf-bdi+bdh+cdh-cge) = 0 \quad \rightarrow (1)$$

$$\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \text{ and } \lambda_3 \text{ are the roots of equation (1).} \quad \rightarrow (2)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = a+e+i \quad \rightarrow (3)$$

$$\lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2 \lambda_3 + \lambda_3 \lambda_1 = ai+ei-gc-hf+ae-bd \quad \rightarrow (4)$$

$$\lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 = aei-ahf-bdi+bdh+cdh-cge \quad \rightarrow (5)$$

The corresponding rhotrix R_3 is $\begin{pmatrix} a & & \\ g & e & c \\ & & i \end{pmatrix}$ and the coupled matrix as reported in is $C = \begin{bmatrix} a & 0 & c \\ 0 & e & 0 \\ g & 0 & i \end{bmatrix}_{3 \times 3}$

We considered the characteristic roots (Eigen values) of R_3 and C will be same.

$$|C - \lambda I| = 0$$

$$\Rightarrow \lambda^3 - (a+e+i)\lambda^2 + (ei+ai-gc-ae)\lambda - (aei-gce) = 0 \quad \rightarrow (5)$$

$$\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3 \text{ are the roots of equation (5)} \quad \rightarrow (6)$$

$$\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \lambda_3 = a+e+i \quad \rightarrow (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_1 \lambda_2 + \lambda_2 \lambda_3 + \lambda_3 \lambda_1 &= ai+ei-gc+ae && \rightarrow(7) \\ \lambda_1 \lambda_2 \lambda_3 &= aei-gce && \rightarrow(8) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem is followed from the equations (2), (3), (4) and (6), (7), (8) respectively.

Numerical Illustration 1:

Consider $A = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & -1 & 1 \\ -1 & 5 & -1 \\ 1 & -1 & 3 \end{bmatrix}$. The corresponding rhotrix is

$$R_3 = \left\langle \begin{array}{c} 3 \\ 1 \ 5 \ 1 \\ 3 \end{array} \right\rangle$$

Finding the given Eigen value of R_3 is equivalent to finding $\lambda \in R$
 Such that

$$\begin{vmatrix} 3-\lambda & 1 \\ 1 & 3-\lambda \end{vmatrix} = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Leftrightarrow \lambda^2 - 6\lambda - 8 &= 0 \\ \Leftrightarrow (\lambda-4)(\lambda-2) &= 0 \\ \Leftrightarrow \lambda &= 2, 4 \end{aligned}$$

Eigen values of R_3 are $\lambda = 2, 4, 5$, considering the third Eigen value as 5, being the sum of Eigen values equal to sum of diagonal elements of rhotrix. Using above theorem

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda'_1 + \lambda'_2 + \lambda'_3 &= 11, \\ \lambda'_1 \lambda'_2 \lambda'_3 &= 36, \\ \lambda'_1 \lambda'_2 + \lambda'_2 \lambda'_3 + \lambda'_3 \lambda'_1 &= 36 \end{aligned}$$

Solving this we get
 $\lambda'_1 = 2, \lambda'_2 = 3, \lambda'_3 = 6$

Numerical illustration 2:

Consider a rhotrix

$$R_5 = \left\langle \begin{array}{c} 1 \\ 1 \ 1 \ 1 \\ 3 \ 2 \ 5 \ 4 \ 3 \\ 1 \ 3 \ 1 \\ 1 \end{array} \right\rangle$$

Now the major matrix is

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 5 & 1 \\ 3 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The eigen values of A are -2,3,6

The eigen vectors corresponding to $\lambda_1 = -2$ is (-2,0,2), $\lambda_2 = 3$ is (-1,1,-1) and $\lambda_3 = 6$ is (1,2,1).

Again for the minor matrix

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}$$

The eigen values of C are 5,-1.

The eigen vectors corresponding to 5 and -1 is (1,1) and (-2,1).

Finding

$$R_5 \langle x^{5j} \rangle = \begin{pmatrix} & & & & 4 \\ & & & & 0 & 5 & -3 \\ -4 & 5 & 3 & 2 & 6 \\ & & & & -3 & -1 & 12 \\ & & & & 6 \\ & & & & 4 \\ & & & & 0 & 5 & -3 \\ -4 & 5 & 3 & 2 & 6 \\ & & & & -3 & -1 & 12 \\ & & & & 6 \end{pmatrix}$$

Therefore $R_5 \langle x^{5j} \rangle = \lambda \langle x^{5j} \rangle, j = 1,2,3$.
 Similarly, $R_5 \langle x^{j5} \rangle = \langle x^{j5} \rangle \lambda, j = 1,2,3$.

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